

Traceological Study of Copper-Alloy Artifacts from the Lusatian Culture Cemetery in Opole-Groszowice, Poland

Copper-based finds from the cemetery in Opole-Groszowice, excavated in 1967 and 1969, were submitted for traceological analysis following their conservation treatment. The artifacts were examined under a portable digital Dino-Lite Edge microscope with a 1,3 Mpx camera, magnification from $\times 20$ to $\times 220$, and a stereoscopic microscope Carl Zeiss Stemi 2000-C with Delta Optical DLT-Cam PRO 2MP camera.

Microscopic Observation Results

Rings (Fig. S1:1, S2)

Rings from graves 143 (inv. no. MŚ-A-9/67/107), 148 (inv. no. MŚ-A-9/67/132) and 152 (inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/40) were examined. Traces that could be linked with a plastic forming of the surface or use-related wear were observed in only one case, the ring from grave 148. They consist of gentle flattening accompanied by a hitting mark. A transverse, relatively deep mark on the hoop of the ring from grave 152 is evidence of an attempt made to cut it.

Pins and bimetallic artifact (Fig. S1:3–5)

The assemblage included five pins and one object resembling a pin. Traces that can be linked to the production process include evidence of plastic forming of the shaft of pins from grave 152 (inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/37) and 154 (inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/48). The ornament at the “base” of the bimetallic object from grave 148 (inv. no. MŚ-A-9/67/133) was executed carelessly. The surface of these objects is poorly preserved, characterized by extensive pitting corrosion.

Looped studs (Fig. S1:6–7)

The looped studs from grave 154 (inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/51) were produced in one piece, that is, both the body of the stud and the loop were cast at the same time. The loop hole was made either by inserting a small ceramic casting core or special tabs inside the casting mold. Forms of this type are known, among others, from the metal hoard discovered at Bieszków in Lubuskie province. Metal overflows next to the edges of the loop holes are evidence for the use of such cores. Some of the studs could have constituted serial production using a multi-matrix casting mold. The place of attachment of the loop to the stud body reveals traces of plastic forming with a tool equipped with a working surface, the shape of which was such that it left even edges. These traces should be linked to the forming of the final button shape by forging (peening?).

Fig. S1. Traces of production and use observed on objects from the cemetery at Opole-Groszowice 1 – flattened places associated with either the forming or the use of the ring (grave 148; inv. no. MŚ-A- 9/67/132); 2 – transverse cut on the hoop of a ring (grave 152; inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/38); 3 – fragment of an iron pin around which the bronze was cast (grave 148; inv. no. MŚ-A-9/67/133); 4 – traces of the bronze running around the pin (grave 154, inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/50); 5 – traces of forging on the pin shaft (grave 152; inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/37); 6 – metal overflow on the edges of a stud loop, linked to the use of a ceramic casting core (grave 154; inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/51); 7 – inner side of a stud body with traces of plastic processing (grave 154; inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/51); 8 – rounded edge of a torque (grave 154; inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/49). Photo K. Nowak

Neck ring (torques) (Fig. S1:8)

Ornaments of this type were made in a multi-step process of preparing a long bar of quadrangular section, which was subsequently twisted around itself. Interprocess annealing was applied as a method to avoid excessive tension in the metal.

The piece from grave 154 (inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/49) is carelessly and irregularly twisted. The extended flattened ends show traces of forging. The edges of the bar, which must have once been sharp, have become rounded in places. This could be the effect of the ornament having been worn.

The damaged piece from grave 149 (inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/9) was also carelessly executed. The other neck ring from the same grave (inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/8) is much better made. The ornament was carefully executed, but the intense twisting and resulting tension has caused a fracturing of the surface.

Fig. S2. Neck ring from grave 149 (inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/7) 1-3 – design errors in ornament execution; 4 – metal patching of a damaged part of the neck ring. Photo K. Nowak

Ankle rings (Fig. S3: 1, 2)

The production technique for the ankle rings from grave 149 (inv. nos MŚO-A-30/69/15 and MŚO-A-30/69/16) was much the same as for the necklace made of sheet bronze. The surfaces of the objects were smooth, unornamented, and uneven in places. This could be due to the

production process as much as everyday use. The thin walls of the pieces are worn through in places.

Needle (Fig. S3:3)

The needle (inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/10) is damaged—the top of the eye is broken—and heavily corroded on the surface. It was produced from a forged metal rod of small section. The rod was bent on itself at one end to form the loop of the needle in the upper part. No use-wear traces of any kind were noted.

Bracelet (Fig. S3:4)

The bracelet (inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/14) was made from a massive piece of metal. The production process started with casting a bar (presumably lens-shaped in section) from tin bronze and then looping it. Some of the ornamental motifs were made at the casting stage, while the more delicate details, such as tiny oblique incisions and circles were added after the bracelet had been cast. The inside wall is highly polished and smooth, possibly by being worn for a long time.

Fig. S3. Traces of production and use observed on objects from the cemetery at Opole-Groszowice. 1-2 – flattened parts of the surface and rounded edges of the gap in the anklets (grave 149; inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/16); 3 – scratch connected with the joining of the wire that was looped to make the eye of the needle (grave 149; inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/10); 4 – detail of the ornament on the bracelet (grave 149; inv. no. MŚO-A-30/69/14): A – trace resulting from casting; B – traces of forming by polishing. Photo K. Nowak